

HISTORICAL AND CONTEMPORARY ANALYSIS OF CIVIL LIBERTIES. THE ROLE OF THE UN IN PROMOTING GLOBAL HUMAN DIGNITY.

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Abstract. *In today's society, we are equally entitled to our human rights without discrimination. But how did we achieve this? How constitutional and natural rights were established or the reasons behind lit have always been the most debated topics of discussion. The urge for the creation of human rights in the past, the establishment of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and also, the United Nation's positive impacts are widely discussed in this scientific article relying on authentic sources. Furthermore, the roles of ombudsmen in order to protect civil liberties in different countries, especially in Uzbekistan are analyzed along with examples.*

Key words: *civil rights, international law, United Nations, Universal Declaration of Human rights, ombudsmen.*

ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЙ И СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ГРАЖДАНСКИХ СВОБОД. РОЛЬ ООН В ПРОДВИЖЕНИИ ГЛОБАЛЬНОГО ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО ДОСТОИНСТВА.

Аннотация. *В современном обществе мы в равной степени имеем право на наши права человека без какой-либо дискриминации. Но как мы этого добились? То, как были установлены конституционные и естественные права, или причины этого всегда были наиболее обсуждаемыми темами дискуссий. Стремление к созданию прав человека в прошлом, принятие Всеобщей декларации прав человека, а также положительное влияние Организации Объединенных Наций широко обсуждаются в этой научной статье с опорой на аутентичные источники. Кроме того, на примерах анализируется роль омбудсменов в защите гражданских свобод в разных странах, особенно в Узбекистане.*

Ключевые слова: *гражданские права, международное право, Организация Объединенных Наций, Всеобщая декларация прав человека, омбудсмены.*

A brief introduction about the basic rights of Citizenship.

Human rights are universally accepted moral norms and values that establish standards of human behavior. Specifically, they should and are often protected by both national and international laws. These rights are considered inherent and inalienable, meaning they belong to every individual simply by virtue of being person since the time they were born, regardless of characteristics like their nationality, ethnicity, religion, or even socio-economic statuses.

They encompass a broad range of political, civil, social, and cultural rights, such as the right to live, freedom, protection against enslavement, access to education whether they are men or women, voting equally in elections that are held in their counties, having access to hospital or foster care when needed, protecting from discrimination, having a right to be considered as "not guilty" until the court decides, not being captured without a court permission for a certain period of time, choosing their housing or access to work, and the list goes on.

Whatever their theoretical justification, basic rights of population refer to a wide continuum of values or capabilities thought to enhance and protect human interests and declared to be universal in character, because they are equally claimed for all human beings, young, old or newly born, present and future. Human rights are a set of principles concerned with equality and fairness.

They recognise our liberty to make choices about our lives and to develop our potential as different individuals, they might be about living a life free from fear, harassment, slavery or discrimination.

Main body

1) Historical point of view regarding the initiation of natural rights. How did it all start?

According to many historians who did the research in the field of civil liberties, the origins of Human Rights are ideally pinpointed to the year 539 BC by the time the troops of Cyrus the Great conquered the so-called place Babylon. This king ordered that all slaves should be freed, and officially declared that all people had the right to choose their own religion. But what's important to note is that he also established the racial equality between different nations, which was the initial step to recognize major human rights.

However, it was not until World War II was over. Less than three decades after the First World War, in which more than 18 million soldiers and civilians were killed, Europe was once again embroiled in a major conflict. The Second World War, which pitted Germany, Japan, and Italy against Great Britain, the United States, and the Soviet Union, engulfed the world in a firestorm of death and destruction far exceeding that of the Great War of 1914-1918.

This was not only a global war, it was a total war in which each nation's entire human and material resources were called into service. About 70 million civilians and fighters were killed vigorously, making World War II the deadliest conflict in the entire human history. Millions of people were left homeless, another millions were enslaved, the majority of the population with a scarce sustenance, the shortage of literally everything because of the war. People started protests against the governors

The terrors of war reinforced the demands of early twentieth century internationalists to establish a global bill of human rights that would obligate „Every state to recognize the equal right of every individual on its territory to life, liberty and property, religious freedom and the use of his own language”

2) United Nations. The Declaration of Human Rights.

After the second World War, governments then committed themselves to establishing the UN, which stands for the United Nations with the primary goal of sustaining peace both internally and internationally, and preventing the upcoming conflicts in the globe. Fundamentally, people wanted to ensure that never again would anyone be unjustly denied life, freedom, food, shelter, and nationality. Four months after the San Francisco Conference ended, the United Nations officially began, on 24 October 1945, an important chronicle in human history. Their charter had been ratified by China, France, the Soviet Union, the United Kingdom, the United States and by a majority of other signatories. Standing on the eastern shore of Manhattan Island, on the banks of New York City's East River, the 18-acre UN Headquarters remains both a symbol of peace and a beacon of hope, which is the UN's headquarters.

The United Nations organisation stated that their primary purpose was to maintain international peace and security, to promote human rights and to provide a forum for discussion of global issues, and up to today, the goals had not been changed. Three years later, The Commission, guided by Eleanor Roosevelt's forceful leadership, captured the world's attention, drafting the 30 articles that now make up the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The Declaration was presented to the world, acting for the first time as a recognized and internationally accepted charter, whose first article states that „All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood."

3) Human rights protectors— Ombudsmen.

Last but not least, in many countries, there are officials called ombudsmen who provide a channel for people to submit complaints against institutions including governments, businesses, organizations, news outlets or even schools without influence from the accused. They conduct fair and unbiased investigations at no cost to the complainant that people have made, and provide solutions in a certain period of time. In Uzbekistan, for instance, in 1995 the rank and the position of Ombudsman was established to provide better consultations for those whose rights were discriminated against. Thus far, there have officially been 3 Ombudsmen, namely Sayyora Sharafovna (1995-2015), Ulug'bek Nasriddinovich (2015-2021) and the one working now Feruza Farhodovna.

To conclude, the main stepping stone to the protection of human rights has took place after the initial years of World War II, which later resulted in the organization of United Nations, the UDHR as well as the rank of Ombudsmen that are vitally important in the modern world to raise the awareness about human dignity.

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